

WEFT-KNITTED GLASS-FIBRE PREFORMS FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: Weft knitted preforms have become increasingly popular in recent years for the processing of composite materials due to their low cost and exceptional mechanical properties. The main attributes of weft-knits for composite materials are their fatigue resistant properties and their ability to conform to complex three-dimensional shapes, either by deep drawing/moulding or by integral knitting techniques. The experimental work reported in this paper examines various physical and mechanical properties of the dry preform with respect to knitting machine settings. The investigation of mechanical properties is directed towards the formability (drapability) of the dry preform in terms of KESF testing and a modified CBR plunger test method. The results demonstrate that both methods may provide useful design parameters of formability for subsequent composite processing.

KEYWORDS: weft-knitted preforms, formability, deep drawing, KESF testing.

INTRODUCTION

The use of textile technology, such as weaving and braiding, in the manufacture of preforms for advanced composite materials has and continues to be under intense investigation due to the potential of these processes to produce low-cost high-quality structures with improved mechanical performance. In recent years, weft-knitted structures have become of increasing interest due to their potential as crash/fatigue resistant materials and their ability to conform to complex three-dimensional shapes. The latter may be derived from deep drawing/moulding techniques utilising the formability properties of the flat preform or by integral knitting techniques to manufacture the near net shape. In this paper, the term formability is preferred to drapability because, in the textile sense, the latter refers to the shape adopted by an initially flat fabric under the effects of gravity loading only rather than by drawing/moulding processes. With integral knitting, the essential preform shape is actually manufactured on the knitting machine with added benefits of low material wastage and low labour costs [1], providing an appropriate machine type is available. While it may seem contradictory in view of the three-dimensional nature of the knitted loop, weft-knitted preforms with inlay yarns/tows can also yield higher strength than that of woven fabrics because the inlay yarns are essentially uncrimped [2].

Reports in the literature have generally been with respect to the mechanical properties of composite test specimens and/or demonstrations of the shaping potential. The basic mechanical properties of weft-knitted composites have been extensively studied. The effect of volume fraction on the properties of weft-knitted composites has been of particular interest

[3]. Methods of increasing the fibre content and stiffness of knitted laminates, together with composite fracture mechanisms has also been studied [4]. Various weft-knitted composite structures have been investigated with respect to stiffness and fatigue resistance [5] and, later, other structures were examined with respect to composite strength [6]. The effect of pre-stretch of the dry preform on composite properties has also been examined [7]. However, there have been no studies carried out on the properties of the dry preform and no formability concepts have been developed for shaping. Yet it has been well established that weft knitting is an excellent candidate for forming complex shapes due to its formability properties. The only related area in which work has been undertaken is for woven fabrics [8].

Knowledge of the mechanical properties and formability of the dry preform is important for providing a systematic engineering approach for weft-knitted preform design and manufacture and subsequent composite fabrication. Work to this end is currently being undertaken by the authors, and progress is reported in this paper.

WEFT KNITTING BACKGROUND

In the textile industry, weft knitting is a well-established fabric-forming technology and a large variety of structures can be manufactured depending upon machine type available [9]. Such structures include simple plain knits, ribs, purls, interlocks and double-knit structures, such as full milano and punto-di-roma, as well as more complex designs in which surface effects and/or colour are developed for apparel applications. For composite applications, the simple and double-knit structures, together with the use of inlay, plating and integral knitting techniques, are likely to be of greatest interest. Fundamental terms used to characterise such weft-knitted structures include the following:

loop length,	L (mm)	= length of yarn to form one complete knitted stitch.
average Lav,	Lav(mm)	= total length of yarn to form one repeat / no. of stitches in one repeat.
course density,	c/cm	= number of horizontal rows of loops per cm.
wale density,	w/cm	= number of vertical columns of loops per cm.
areal density,	g/m ²	= mass of fabric in grams / area of fabric in sqm.
tightness factor,	K	= $\sqrt{\text{tex} / \text{Lav}}$
run-in-ratio,	L ₁ :L ₂	= ratio of loop lengths in one structural repeat.
Tex,	T	= linear density in g/km

Available in the textile literature are many studies on the geometry and structural mechanics of weft-knitted fabrics as well as the mechanics of fabric formation. They emphasise the importance of loop length and run-in-ratio in the control of fabric dimensions and of other basic physical properties such as areal density. Such studies were initially carried out on plain fabrics [10] and later on double jersey constructions [11]. Further, these properties are dependent upon the existence of various relaxation states for the fabric due to such factors as the visco-elastic nature of most textile fibres, the effects of inter-fibre friction and the subsequent finishing treatments that may be applied to the fabric. Investigations into the mechanics of weft knitting have shown that the variables of most importance in controlling loop length are the stitch cam setting, the input tension setting, the fabric take-down tension, and the yarn-metal friction [12]. The development of weft-knitted preforms composed of high performance fibres must therefore recognise this pre-existing knowledge. The knittability of high performance yarns has been shown to be dependent upon the frictional

properties, pliability and strength of the yarn [13]. Glass fibres are very brittle in nature, have high stiffness and high coefficient of friction, and consequently require a low input tension, tension control and minimal metal surface contact for knitting.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A range of full milano rib structures together with their plain knit and 1x1 rib components (see Figure 1) were manufactured on an 8-gauge (E8) Stoll ANVH/BLM-es knitting machine - this is a computer-controlled rib-jacquard V-bed machine which uses the Sintral programming language.

Figure 1: a) Full Milano b) 1x1 Rib, c) plain tubular jersey nomenclature

These structures were produced with 68 x 2 tex glass fibre tows with silane size from Silenka Glass Yarns. Yarn input tension and fabric take-down tension were set at minimal values consistent with good knitting performance. In addition, the yarn feed path was linearised and metal contact surfaces polished to reduce the effects of abrasion on the glass fibres. Different values of stitch cam settings were set to produce different loop lengths within the preform structures. All preforms were allowed to relax under standard ambient conditions of 25°C, 65% relative humidity for a minimum of 24 hours prior to testing. Sampling was carried out in accordance with the Australian standard for testing and then quantified in terms of their loop lengths, areal density, wale and course densities, thickness [14] and tightness factor. These physical tests were followed by mechanical testing on the Kawabata Evaluation System for Fabrics (KES-FB) instrumentation, which was initially developed for fabric objective measurement in the textile and clothing industries, and a simple formability test based on the CBR burst test for geotextiles.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of KES-FB instrumentation

The four fabric mechanical properties assessed using the KES-FB instrumentation are in-plane tension, in-plane shear, transverse compression and out of plane bending as shown in Figure 2. These instruments are designed to take measurements at low stress levels whilst providing data on a wide range of parameters including deformation and recovery for each mechanical property obtained [15]. The operating procedure for the KESF instrumentation is given elsewhere [16]. Figure 3 gives a typical representation of the deformation/recovery

curves for a fabric subjected to extension or lateral compression and bending or shear in KESF testing.

Figure 3: a) in-plane tension and transverse compression, b) in-plane shear and out-of plane bending

The important features of the curves are that they are non-linear and exhibit hysteresis; the latter implies that energy is lost during the deformation cycle. The hysteresis is shown by the shaded areas in the graphs and is due to inter-fibre friction effects and the visco-elastic behaviour of the fibres [15]. In the textile and clothing industries, the following standard parameters have been defined from these curves [16]:

tensile	LT	tensile linearity	WT/area $Q_1Q_2Q_3$	%
	WT	tensile energy	area $Q_1 A Q_2Q_3$	J/m ²
	RT	tensile resilience	area $Q_1 B Q_2Q_3$ /WT	%
	EMT	tensile extensibility	Q_3	%
shear	G	shear rigidity	slope Rig	Nm/m ²
	2HG	hysteresis of shear force at 0.5°	width of Hys	N/m
	2HG5	hysteresis of shear force at 5°	width of Hys	N/m
bending	B	bending rigidity	slope Rig	μNm
	2HB	hysteresis of bending moment	width of Hys	μNm
compression	LC	compressional linearity	WC/area $Q_1Q_2Q_3$	%
	WC	compressional energy	area $Q_1 A Q_2Q_3$	J/m ²
	RC	compressional resilience	area $Q_1 B Q_2Q_3$ /WC	%
	EMC	compressibility	Q_3	%

The simple formability test was based on the CBR burst strength test for geotextiles [17]. In this test, a cylindrical plunger is forced through the centre of a circular specimen which is gripped around its entire circumference by clamps in a loading frame; Figure 4 illustrates the plunger and clamping arrangements. The plunger displacement and reactive force are recorded. In the present case, the plunger is taken to a maximum displacement of 50 mm rather than to specimen failure (burst); the plunger displacement speed was set to 20 mm/min.

Figure 4. Plunger and clamping arrangement for the CBR test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the physical property tests are given in Table 1 where L_r and L_p refer to the stitch cam settings on the knitting machine for the rib courses and the plain knit courses, respectively. From these tables, it is clear that larger loop lengths result from increasing the stitch cam settings for all three knit structure types, although the run-in-ratio decreases for the milano structures. Further, the increase in loop length(s) yields reductions in areal density, tightness factor, and wale and course densities. In the case of thickness, however, the effect is dependent upon knit structure as the loop length is increased, with thickness decreasing for the milano fabrics and increasing for the plain knit and rib fabrics.

Table 1 Preform physical properties

PREFORM	M3	M61	M9	R3	R6	R9	P61	P9
g/sqm	670	601	434	742	607	504	396	290
L_r (mm)	6.6	7.3	8.7	6.6	7.6	9.2	N/A	N/A
L_p (mm)	5.8	6.7	9	N/A	N/A	N/A	6.6	8.9
$2L_r:L_p$	2.28	2.17	1.93	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
L_{av}	6.1	6.9	8.9	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
C/cm	8.9	8.2	6.5	9.9	7.8	6.9	8.3	6.6
W/cm	4.45	3.65	2.65	4.25	3.6	2.9	4.8	3.3
Thickness (mm)	2.35	2.19	1.98	2.04	2.30	2.59	1.14	1.35
K	1.92	1.64	1.27	1.77	1.53	1.27	1.77	1.31
L_r (setting)	8.1	9.5	11	8.1	9.5	11	N/A	N/A
L_p (setting)	10.1	11	13	N/A	N/A	N/A	11	13

The results were not only informative of the preforms' physical properties but also provided an insight into the interaction between machine, yarn/tow and the structure being knitted. The milano fabric M3 is at the limits of the knitting capabilities of the machine, ie. milano fabric could not be knitted at smaller stitch cam settings due to excessive yarn/tow breaks, dropped stitches and knitting needle damage. The results for eight additional milano fabrics (not reported here) emphasise this knittability limit in terms of stitch cam settings. Although this limit was not directly explored for the plain knit and rib structures, it is notable that the plain knit structure P3 could not be knitted even though its component in the milano M3 was successfully manufactured at the low stitch cam setting, $L_p=10.1$. Further, while the results in Table 1 indicate a general correlation between the various physical parameters of the milano

structures and their plain knit and rib components, it is notable that the rib loop lengths differ between the rib and milano structures at the higher stitch cam settings. These phenomena can be explained with reference to the “robbing back theory” [12] which states that the loop length achieved is dependent on the maximum tension developed in the knitting zone associated with the stitch cam. This maximum tension is essentially constant (allowing for statistical variabilities) when knitting simple structures such as plain knit and 1x1 rib. In the case of full milano rib, the maximum tension alternates from the value of the plain loop components for two courses to that of the rib loop components for one course. In addition, the unstable nature of the plain knit fabrics required a higher take-up tension to overcome the unbalanced internal forces inherent to these structures. This higher take-up tension would increase the maximum tension within the knitting zone and yield higher loop lengths. In fact, this principle also accounts for the plain loop lengths being slightly smaller in the plain knit and the rib loop lengths being slightly larger in the 1x1 rib as compared to the corresponding component values in the milano fabrics.

The results of the KES-FB tests are summarised in Figs 5-14 for three milano structures. It is to be noted that the hysteresis (energy loss) for all mechanical properties was substantially higher than for most apparel fabrics (approximately 10-fold). It is highly probable that these hysteresis losses are due to inter-fibre friction as the fibres are essentially elastic. Further, the fabrics display some permanent deformation upon removal of load. This is emphasised in Fig. 15 which presents the results of a number of tensile cycles on one specimen.

Figure 5: Compression linearity & resilience

Figure 6: Compressional energy

Figure 7: Bending rigidity

Figure 8: Hysteresis of bending moment

Figure 9: Shear rigidity

Figure 10: Shear hysteresis

Figure 11: Tensile linearity and resilience

Figure 12: Tensile energy

Figure 13: Tensile extensibility

Figure 14: Compressibility

Figure 15: Tension deformation/recovery curve

Figure 16: Helicopter door track pocket composite

In general, increasing the tightness of the fabric results in hysteresis and rigidity increases for the shear and bending properties. In the case of tensile and compressional behaviour, the hysteresis energy can be determined from the following relation,

$$\text{hysteresis energy loss} = Wx (1-Rx) \text{ where } x = T(\text{tensile}), C(\text{compression}).$$

Thus, compressional hysteresis also increases as the fabric tightness is increased and this is accompanied by a decrease in the compressional strain due to the increased quantity of fibre opposing the deformation. In the case of the tensile tests, increasing fabric tightness tends to decrease the load extension curve, with the middle tightness fabric showing a maximum in tensile linearity and resilience, and energy and hysteresis in the course direction, together with a minimum in tensile extensibility, and energy and hysteresis in the wale direction. Further work is currently being undertaken to examine these effects in terms of run-in-ratio as well as fabric tightness.

Fig. 16 illustrates a composite part of complex shape produced by deep-drawing a glass fibre milano preform with subsequent matrix impregnation by resin transfer moulding (RTM). Examination of fabric distortions in the final composite emphasise complex strain fields exhibiting high fabric shear and in-plane extensibility, together with areas of high curvature. Laboratory simulation of the deep-drawing process can be undertaken using formability tests such as that previously described.

Figure 17: Milano: Formability/energy

Figure 18 Milano: Formability/displacement

Figure 19: Plain: Formability/displacement

Figure 20: Rib: Formability/displacement

The results of these tests are shown in Figs 17-20 for the three milano structures and their rib and plain knit components. With increasing tightness factor, the total energy yielded increases as does the slope of the load-displacement curves for all fabric structures tested. This is consistent with the above results for physical and mechanical behaviour. Interestingly, the results also suggest that the plain knit components are the dominating factor for determining resistance to load for the milano structures.

CONCLUSION

The results reported in this paper demonstrate that there is a definite interplay between the physical properties of weft-knitted preforms and knitting machine settings through study of the working limits of the loop length dimensions together with replications of these settings in different structures.

The mechanical properties derived from the KESF testing are useful for determining the engineering formability of knit structures for subsequent composite processing. However, all tensile, shear, bending and compressive properties complement one another for this purpose. The simpler design parameters for assessing the formability offered by the modified CBR plunger test method require further investigation. Such work is in progress.

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